

Managing cost drivers: the case of RESOLVE project

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KEYWORDS

Cost drivers
Modularity
Scalability
Electric L-Category Vehicles (ELVs)
RESOLVE

Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to discuss how cost drivers can be analyzed and managed; particularly the focus is on the product design configuration.

Design/methodology/approach – This is a constructive case study (Kasanen et al., 1993).

Findings – The empirical domain of this paper is the dynamic and complex electric mobility scenario. The focus is on the RESOLVE project, funded by the European's Union research and innovation program¹; RESOLVE aims to find technological and design solutions suitable for a wide range of Electric L-Category Vehicles (ELV), culminating in two demonstrator vehicles. To date, the wide diffusion of fully electric vehicles is delayed by several limiting factors, among which powertrain's cost is the most relevant. RESOLVE will face cost reduction in several ways: by modular and scalable design of the components (i.e. battery pack), through functional integration for drivetrain electronics as well as using existing low-cost solutions for few devices.

Research implications/limitations – The case analysis suggests guidelines for analyzing cost drivers and using cost information to support this process; other researches are needed to extend the conclusions in different contexts.

Practical implications – Understanding cost driver relevance and manageability contributes to increase the effectiveness of cost reduction through design. Selecting relevant cost drivers and relative suitable cost information could support management in identifying possible levers in order to reduce costs and may play a role in developing sustainable solutions in the automotive sector.

Originality/value – The paper tries to improve our understanding about cost driver selection and management.

Paper type: Research paper.

RESOLVE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement nr. 653511.

¹ RESOLVE: Range of Electric SOLUTIONS for L-Category VEHICLES - Horizon2020- GV5 2014 - Grant Agreement nr 653511 (<http://www.resolve-project.eu/>).

Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to discuss how cost drivers can be analyzed and managed. Specifically, the focus is on defining a process of cost driver analysis to be applied within early stages of new product development (NPD), a process characterized by high degree of market, technological and project scope uncertainty (Davila, 2000). First, it is necessary specifying what analysis and management of cost drivers means within this research. In the perspective of this paper, “*analysis*” includes activities such as selection and drill down of cost drivers. Instead, “*managing cost drivers*” refers to a set of initiatives useful to moderate and/or mediate the impact of cost drivers on costs.

Due to this meaning of cost driver analysis, main research questions are:

- “How cost drivers can be analyzed and managed within early stages of NPD to overcome cost constraints?”
- “Which cost information can support these activities?”

Within strategy and management accounting literature cost driver is a well-known concept examined from many perspectives; however, their selection during early stages of NPD is not investigated in depth. Porter (1985), Shank (1989), Shank and Govindarajan (1993), considered value chain, positioning and strategic issues and they dealt mainly with the costs and performance of activities. These authors defined several classifications of cost drivers but a detailed process to analyze of relevant cost drivers still lacks. Another research stream is focused mainly on identifying cost drivers within activity based costing system, in order to improve accuracy of cost allocation (e.g. Garvin, 1997; Bjornenak, 2000; Homburg, 2001; Sheng 2009; Cokins and Capusneau, 2010; Wang et al. 2010; Kaplan and Cooper, 1998)

Cost drivers selection and management during early stages of NPD is a relevant activity due to the impact that it could have on the product costs (Cooper and Slagmulder, 1999). Often in some contexts selecting relevant cost drivers is not a problem, since they are evident, but in others, it may be difficult, due to, for instance, the complex relationships among cost drivers and between cost drivers and cost objects. Identification of cost drivers during early stages of NPD permits to highlight causes of cost and consequently to model cost modifying product and/or process design configuration. Target costing is a well-known technique adopted to support cost reduction during NPD (Ansari et al., 2006; Davila and Wouters, 2007). Anyway, target costing shows scarce effectiveness when there are complex cost behaviors and/or high uncertainty about product design configuration (Davila and Wouters, 2007). In these environments, cost reduction during early stages of NPD could be carried out also applying other initiatives, such as part commonalities, design for assembly, for usability. In these cases, is not clear the linkage with cost drivers, the kind and role of cost information used to support product and process design configuration.

Particularly adopting a case study method, this paper wishes to extend previous knowledge by providing new evidence on the topic of cost driver selection and management during early stages of NPD.

The empirical domain is the electric mobility scenario; specifically the focus is on RESOLVE projects that aims to develop two demonstrators belonging to Electric Light Vehicle category (ELV), called L2 and L6, and to find technological and design solutions suitable for a wide range of full L-category vehicles. Furthermore, through the case of RESOLVE project, we explore characteristics of relevant cost information at the early stages of NPD and we propose a qualitative model to support the analysis of relationships among cost drivers.

The paper is organized as follows: it begins with a literature review on cost driver analysis and early stages of NPD, then, it describes research method, empirical domain and main case findings. Finally, it discusses results, limitations and it provides suggestions for further researches.

Literature review

The literature dealing with cost driver could be clustered within three mainstreams: i) cost driver analysis along the value chain and for strategic purposes; ii) cost driver selection to improve cost calculation, generally by activity-based costing techniques; iii) the relationship among technology, product characteristics and cost drivers. According to the purposes of this paper, the first and the third mainstreams are particularly useful, since this paper not deal with cost calculation accuracy.

About cost driver analysis along value chain, Porter (1985) introduced the term *cost driver* referring to what determines cost of activities value chain, in order to analyze cost behavior and to stress the importance of analyzing costs across a firm's entire value chain. The concept of "strategic cost driver" refers to move beyond the notion that volume drives cost, generally applied in a market based on the mass production of a mature product with known characteristics and stable technology. About the selection process of relevant cost drivers Porter (1985: 87-88) claimed that several methods to identify cost drivers exist, such as analyzing basic economical features of a value added activity, examining internal experience of the firm and historical data, interviewing managers and experts and, lastly, comparing costs of a value added activity of the firm with competitors' cost structure. Furthermore, Porter (1985: 92) applied his cost driver classification to procurement; he defined and described drivers of the unit cost of purchased inputs. For example, the cost driver "Economies of scale" is called "Purchasing scale" if it is applied to procurement. This cost refers to "*the volumes of purchasing with a given supplier that can affect bargaining power*" (Porter, 1985: 92). The author argued that understanding the cost behavior of key suppliers can allow a firm performing better purchasing policies and better exploiting linkages with suppliers.

Shank (1989) underlined the importance of analyzing costs in terms of extended value chain, the close relationship between the objective of cost analysis and strategic positioning and lastly he argued that cost behavior should be understood as a function of strategic choices.

Shank (1989) and Shank and Govindarajan (1993) included cost driver analysis, value chain analysis and strategic positioning analysis as the three main issues in Strategic Cost Management (SCM). It can be defined as "*the managerial use of cost information explicitly directed at one or more of the four stages of the strategic management cycle*" (Shank, 1989: 50). Cost behavior and cost structure in the organization depend on strategic choices affecting the so-called structural cost drivers. Shank (1989) and Shank and Govindarajan (1993) argued that cost behavior depends on the complex interplay among cost drivers. Furthermore, the authors (1993: 284) examined executional cost drivers in order to verify if they reinforce or mitigate the impact of structural cost drivers. Finally, Shank and Govindarajan, (1996: 26) underlined the need to align researches on cost drivers with those regarding cost accounting techniques.

Hence, according to previous literature it is possible to put in evidence at least the following elements:

- sometime cost drivers selection is not a problem since causes of costs are evident, while in other circumstances this activity could be performed through a "portfolio of approaches" such as interviews, cost data analysis, benchmark with competitors; anyway, the topic is not addressed in depth, considering a context such as early stages of NPD;
- cost information is linked to cost driver analysis in many ways: product costing or more in general cost calculation should be consistent with cost driver behavior (e.g. if volume is a significant cost driver, costing techniques should be based on this parameters, instead if volume isn't the main cost driver, also costing techniques should be adjusted; furthermore if economies of scale or learning are relevant cost drivers, cost information have to highlight their effect)

Regarding relationship among cost drivers, a stream of literature dealt with technology, product characteristics and costs. Particularly Banker et al. (1990) Greer and Moses (1992), Banker and Johnston (1993), Datar et al. (1993) developed and estimated multivariate equation models of cost driver systems to capture relationships between activity drivers and costs, focusing on product and process design variables. Specifically, Banker et al. (1990) focused on the role of product design

configuration in determining Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and they discussed about the strategic importance of understanding the impact of product and process complexity on costs for improving and innovating product design configuration to reduce costs and to increase value for customers (Banker and Johnston, 2007: 541). Greer and Moses (1992) dealt with the role of technology as a structural driver of new product development costs and of production costs. Banker and Johnston (1993) showed the managerial and statistical relevance of product diversity and process complexity. Datar et al. (1993) developed a simultaneous equation model to examine the relationships among four major categories of overhead costs and eight cost drivers related to product complexity and process design. However, none of these mentioned authors developed a model to support management in identifying relevant cost driver relationships.

Hence, cost driver analysis could be useful to revise strategy and value chain also during the new product development (NPD). Previous researches have found that a significant percentage, approximately 80%, of product costs are determined at the product development stage (Berliner and Brimson, 1991; Yoshikawa et al., 1993; Cooper & Slagmulder, 1999). At the early stages of NPD there is usually a high degree of technological, market and project scope uncertainty (Davila, 2000) and an accurate selection process of cost drivers may be useful in order to identify levers to be moved e.g. for cost reduction and cost management. Regarding cost information useful to overcome cost constraints and more in general to manage costs during early stages of NPD, Davila and Wouters (2007) argued that in environments with complex cost behaviors it could be more useful to limit cost models to direct costs rather than adopting more sophisticated and complex costing systems. Since in the early stages of development there is a high degree of uncertainty in cost estimations, it is not possible having cost information with high level of accuracy, therefore a cost management technique such as target costing may lose its effectiveness (Davila and Wouters, 2007). However, it is better to take care of costs early, before the decision in favor of solution is made, in order to be effective in the cost reduction effort (Ehrlenspiel, 2010, p. 62). Then preliminary cost analysis is relevant because if there is a first idea of costs in the early stages of a product life, it is possible to check if planned target cost is reached, and make changes or interventions at the beginning of development process, when they are cheaper.

Problems about preliminary cost estimation and reduction have been addressed mostly from an operations point of view where several practices (such as Design for X (DFX) techniques—for instance, design for manufacturing, design for recycling, etc.) have been examined. These techniques aim to maximize profitability of a product over its lifecycle, focusing on cost reduction (Davila and Wouters, 2007: 834). However, it is not explored how these initiatives could be connected to the cost drivers mentioned in the strategic and management accounting literature (e.g. cost drivers according to Porter, Shank and Govindarajan) and which kind of cost information is adopted to sustain these initiatives. In fact, having information about the impact on total cost of the product of shared resources may be useful for companies in defining their product design configuration (e.g. if and how the product configuration may be applied to a wide range of products that will be developed in the next future).

This research deals with mentioned issues adopting the “lens” of cost management; in fact, herein the focus is exploring which cost information may be useful in early stages of NPD in order to gain cost reduction working on the cost driver “product design configuration”. This research also shows the relevance of well-known approaches widely explored in engineering, operational but also in management accounting literature (Davila and Wouters, 2004), such as modularity, focusing on exploring its usefulness as cost reduction approach in early stages of NPD. Furthermore, the paper puts in evidence the role of cost information in product design configuration when commonality policies are adopted in designing products.

Method

We answer to the research questions using the case study method. It is well known that case studies are suited to answer “how” and “why” questions. Case study analysis typically combines a variety of data collection methods such as analysis of archival materials, observations, interviews, questionnaires, mixing quantitative and qualitative techniques (Eisenhardt, 1989). Besides case studies are useful when the researcher investigate complex and dynamic phenomena which include many variables, some not quantifiable (Cooper and Morgan, 2008). In this research, we follow a constructive approach (Kasanen et. al, 1993). “*The constructive approach means problem solving through the construction of organizational procedures or models*” (Kasanen et. al, 1993: 244). This approach is a research procedure for producing constructions². In management accounting, it is intended to produce managerial constructions. The research process may be defined as follows (Kasanen et. al. 1993):

- 1) Find a practically relevant problem, which also has research potential.
- 2) Obtain a general and comprehensive understanding of the topic.
- 3) Innovate, i.e., construct a solution idea.
- 4) Show the theoretical connections and the research contribution of the solution concept.
- 5) Demonstrate that the solution works.
- 6) Examine the scope of applicability of the solution.

This paper collects and analyzes empirical evidences triangulating three sources of evidence (Abernethy et al., 2005) as document analysis, brainstorming and interviews performed with managers involved in RESOLVE project. Main source of data of this research consists on document analysis, specifically the Grant Agreement of the project (Horizon2020- GV5 2014 - Grant Agreement nr. 653511), deliverables performed by partners from May 2015-to date within several work packages, and presentations performed by partners involved during past Consortium meetings. The case of RESOLVE project is useful in developing the construct reported in this study and in providing a comprehensive understanding of the topic. As we mentioned above, this paper represents an intermediate step of a broader research. We are at stage four of the constructive research process; next steps will be testing the solution³ and examining the generalizability to other contexts.

Empirical domain and case findings

The empirical domain of this paper is the electric mobility scenario. Specifically the focus is on process of cost driver selection and management in the early stages of development of Electric L-Category Vehicles (ELVs) in order to identify possible levers for cost reduction in this dynamic and complex context. Cost and profitability pressures, social and environmental issues (Thrane and Berhausen, 2012) create a setting characterized by high levels of uncertainty, regarding market, technology and scope of the project (Davila, 2000). Congestion of European cities, due to the demand and usage of motor vehicles of a growing urban population, produces noise and emissions levels that pollute the urban environment and that negatively affect the quality of life and health within the cities. L-Category Vehicles (LVs) may represent a solution to limit these factors. Urban policies should encourage more ELV adoption but four limiting factors are preventing their diffusion: cost (and consequently price for end user), energy efficiency, attractiveness and willingness to use. In many cases, they do not provide a superior experience to the rider in terms of comfort, handling, stability and so on (Horizon2020- GV5 2014 - Grant Agreement nr 653511 – Part B). Nowadays due to all mentioned reasons, the rate of adoption of ELVs is still low and they do not have a significant impact on the improvement in urban living conditions.

² Constructions refer in general terms, to entities which produce solutions to explicit problems (Kasanen et. al., 1993: 244)

³ Kasanen et al. (1993:253) defined three kinds of “market test”: weak market test, semi-strong market test, strong market test.

The case study of this research is RESOLVE project, funded by the European’s Union Research and Innovation program⁴. This project is classified as a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) that means referring to:

“Activities aiming to establish new knowledge and/or to explore the feasibility of a new or improved technology, product, process, service or solution. For this purpose, they may include basic and applied research, technology development and integration, testing and validation on a small-scale prototype in a laboratory or simulated environment. Projects may contain closely connected but limited demonstration or pilot activities aiming to show technical feasibility in a near to operational environment”.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/wp/2016_2017/annexes/h2020-wp1617-annex-d-ria_en.pdf

RESOLVE aims at enabling the development of a range of cost-effective, energy efficient and comfortable ELVs that will induce also Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) car drivers to switch from cars to ELVs for their daily urban mobility needs. Compared to a current non-electric LV or car, ELVs have to be competitive on price in order to attract a large consumer base.

Figure 1 shows an overview of the output of the project that consists on the production of two tilting four wheelers demonstrator ELVs (L2e and L6e category), though a large number of acquired advances will also be applicable to the complete range of ELVs (including powered-two wheelers).

Figure 1: L-Category Market overview (Grant Agreement - Part B: 13).

In order to allow a wide diffusion of L-vehicles the RESOLVE project proposes innovative solutions, with advanced safety and comfort features, aiming at increasing ELVs attractiveness. Furthermore, RESOLVE takes into account also female riders’ needs, a user’s group actually underrepresented in the L-category segment and the project represents a chance to redress the balance between male and female adopters.

Energy efficiency is another constraints and it will be increased by lightweight design, optimizing transmission losses and regenerative braking, taking into account vehicle geometry and driving conditions.

⁴ Horizon2020- GV5 2014 - Grant Agreement nr 653511. Consortium Partners are: Piaggio & C. Spa, Austrian Institute Of Technology Gmbh, Robert Bosch Gmbh, Ceske Vysoke Uceni Technicke V Praze, Idiada Automotive Technology Sa, Kiska Gmbh, Ktm Ag, Magneti Marelli S.P.A., Re:Lab S.R.L., Ricardo Deutschland Gmbh, University of Florence, University of Pisa, Wamtechnik Spolka Z Ograniczona Odpowiedzialnoscia, The University Of Warwick.

To increase the willingness to use by urban users, RESOLVE aims to improve drivers experience, in terms of safety and comfort, making advancements to the handling and stability of ELVs (e.g. tilting four wheelers architecture) together with improving the user interface (e.g. providing advices on road surface status, riding style and giving riders accurate information regarding the vehicle range).

Grant Agreement underlines that focus of RESOLVE projects is on electric powertrain and its components: battery pack, drivetrain electronics and electric motor.

Figure 2 illustrates components having a cost constraint to be faced and that will be developed through several solutions to gain cost reductions.

Figure 2: Illustration of components that could be integrated, used from existing technologies or synergized. (Grant Agreement - Part B: 8).

RESOLVE will develop innovative electrified powertrain and it will face cost reduction by:

- modular and scalable design of the components (i.e. battery pack and inverter);
- functional integration for drivetrain electronics, that includes inverter, DC/DC-converter, battery charger and vehicle management unit;
- using existing low-cost solutions for few devices.

These cost reduction approaches are presented by analyzing the content of Grant Agreement and information gathered by meetings with managers of two OEMs involved in the RESOLVE project.

About cost reduction by modularity, this solution refers to battery pack.

The battery system is the element that has the highest impact on the total cost of the E-vehicles. Battery system represents the main economic problem in development and production of Electric vehicles; in addition, it is a component with high degree of technological uncertainty (Kley et al., 2011: 3398). Currently the most widely used in the automotive field are lithium batteries, since they have high performance in terms of long durability and high energy density (Boston Consulting Group, 2009: 3).

Grant Agreement (Part B: 4) highlights that RESOLVE will not directly address battery cost expressed in €/kWh, as this cost will mainly depend on the battery chemistry nowadays not

modifiable. The project aims to reduce the cost of energy storage by designing modular battery architecture, and by reducing the required battery capacity for a target range through energy-saving measures.

RESOLVE will develop modular battery design, suitable for a wide range of ELVs. In fact, this will be fitted into models of different LVs, widening its usage and therefore its production volume. This solution allows reducing unit incidence of design and development costs.

Furthermore, in RESOLVE project, the choice of using a lower voltage battery pack allows most powertrain electronics to be classified as low-voltage systems and it permits to avoid extra costs in safety measures due to a higher voltage.

“RESOLVE will develop a new generation of electrified powertrains that has more functional integration and is modular across ELVs. The modularity will allow these components to be used in a range of vehicles with different engine power” Grant Agreement (Part B: 7).

About cost reduction by scalability, RESOLVE will develop a scalable design for the inverter. It means that this component will be able to drive motors with different power, without modifying hardware component but only through efforts of software reconfiguration.

Cost reduction by functional integration, will be carried out integrating components of the drivetrain electronics (inverter, DC/DC-converter, battery charger and vehicle management unit) into one configurable Drivetrain Management Module (DMM), as well as the Battery Management System (BMS) into the battery pack. This integration allows a further manufacturing and assembly cost reduction.

Grant Agreement (Part B: 8) mentions another approach to gain cost savings that is transferring low-cost solutions from existing technologies in automobiles; this reduces time and effort needed and avoids incurring of additional development costs.

Therefore, costs reduction efforts focus on developing new product design configurations, rather than searching innovative technological solutions.

Following sentences (Horizon2020- GV5 2014 - Grant Agreement nr 653511 – Part B: 4) show that within the RESOLVE project a marginal⁵ cost approach is adopted. A more complete cost configuration is not taken into account and initiatives of cost reduction focus mainly on marginal manufacturing cost.

“Marginal unit manufacturing costs of electric powertrains are comprised of three main components: the battery pack, drivetrain electronics and electric motor”.

“We aim to reduce the marginal unit manufacturing cost of our (omissis) reference design (omissis) to (omissis), down from (omissis), for design volumes of (omissis) units/year”.

Up to now, within RESOLVE project a preliminary cost analysis was carried out. It allowed calculating a preliminary amount of production cost for the two demonstrators, L2e and L6e and comparing these costs to a range of possible market prices. Although target price will be defined in the next stages of the project, when several issues, e.g. product architecture, marketing strategies and so on will be more precisely defined, calculating a rough estimation of the amount of production costs makes the companies aware if there is (or not) a “potential profit margin”

The scheme for estimating product cost in preliminary cost analysis was not a marginal cost but “a partial full cost”. Indeed this cost includes raw material costs, direct depreciation and transformation costs (it does not include development costs and non-manufacturing costs). This cost information allowed knowing both marginal cost and a “partial full cost” that could be more useful at this stage

⁵ *“Marginal unit cost = cost of every additional unit produced (excluding any sunk costs, such as R&D, design, etc.)”* (Horizon2020- GV5 2014 - Grant Agreement nr 653511 – Part B: 4).

for having an idea of the amount of resources needed to realize the products under development. Estimated cost data are mainly based on a rough estimation due to the high degree of uncertainty characterizing these early stages of the project; hence, a new estimation carried out during next stages of the project could change the actual costs. When design activities will permit to reduce uncertainty about the vehicle architecture and systems complexity, allocation of development and non-manufacturing costs will be reconsidered.

Discussion

Through the analysis of existing literature and case findings, we can make some considerations.

RESOLVE case study shows the relevance of the position of the organization within the extended value chain when a cost driver analysis is carried out. In fact it could be different referring e.g. to OEMs, to Tier1 suppliers, to dealers or to consulting firms and research centers (such as Universities) which provide support in R&D activities. In this paper, we explore the topic adopting OEMs' perspective, assuming that certain conclusions could be extended to the entire supply chain.

RESOLVE case study can help to define a method to adopt when a cost problem at early stages of NPD has to be faced. Within the project the cost object (the electric powertrain), presenting cost problems to be faced, is decomposed into subsystems or components, where it could be easier reasoning about cost issues (e.g. due to their simpler architecture and opportunities of cost reductions they highlight) and it could be possible to find solutions for reducing their cost. In addition these sub-components may be classified as cost drivers, since they (and their costs) determine cost of the whole cost object considered.

This way to face the cost reduction issue, is suggesting that the first step in cost driver analysis could be identifying relevant cost driver in the context examined according to some classification suitable to identify cost (e.g. Porter or Riley's classification previously described). Then it can be useful decomposing them again in order to identify sub-cost driver categories, in order to verify if at sub-levels there are major opportunities to manage the cost problem.

Analysis of the RESOLVE project shows the most relevant cost driver in the context examined is the product design configuration (included in Policy choices within Porter's classification and within executional cost drivers within Riley's taxonomy). Particularly within the two demonstrators, cost reduction efforts focus on electric powertrain. In turn, this cost constraint is faced by decomposing it in its components: battery pack, drivetrain electronics and electric motor. The next step is the reduction of incidence of fixed costs of these components through commonalities (Ehrlenspiel et al., 2010). More in detail modularity, scalability and functional integrations has been applied. Particularly modularity has been planned for the battery (Figure 3); having a battery composed of many modules allows choosing the suitable number of modules to get the right power for different vehicles.

Figure 3: a) battery basic module; b) and c) battery pack examples.

Furthermore, modular design permits to avoid further development cost of batteries with different power, because the “right power” could be selected just assembling more modules. In this way, development cost are restricted to those of the modules and these costs can be shared among several modules that will be part of batteries of different kinds of vehicles. Hence, in this case modularity is a way to obtain scale economies and to minimize incidence of development cost per unit. Ehrlenspiel et al. (2010: 318-319) mentioned cost reduction as one of the advantages of modular design. They defined two kind of cost reduction. The first is a so-called *cost reduction for the customers* that happens when they must buy the basic elements only once and the special elements can be added in a second moment. The second, called *cost reduction for manufacturer* consists in producing some components that may be installed in several systems, or different products, therefore they can be produced in larger quantities, gaining volume and scale economies.

Several authors (e.g. Baldwin & Clark, 2000; Schilling, 2000; Davila and Wouters, 2004) dealt with the concept of modularity as an approach to manage costs within projects). Davila and Wouters (2004; 2007) mentioned the modularity approach applied to no core components or sub-systems that are not critical to the main competitive dimension of the project and, as consequence, of the product. Instead, within RESOLVE project, the modular design regards the battery system, a key component of the electric vehicles.

Scalability applied within RESOLVE project concerns the inverter; developing the inverter by a scalable design makes this component able to drive motors with different power, without modifying hardware component but only through efforts of software reconfiguration. In addition, in this case, scalability is a way to reduce incidence of development cost per unit and of other indirect manufacturing cost per unit since it is possible increasing capacity utilization of machineries that produce the physical component (the inverter).

As described in the previous section, cost reduction by functional integration is achieved integrating components of the drivetrain electronics (inverter, DC/DC-converter, battery charger and vehicle management unit) into one configurable Drivetrain Management Module (DMM). This solution reduces manufacturing and assembly costs.

Solutions planned in the RESOLVE project are useful also to get some light on process to carry out in order to select cost drivers to be managed. As underlined above, the electric powertrain is the major cost driver (as sub-system of the vehicle) of electric vehicle. It includes the battery pack, drivetrain electronics and electric motor that are in turn cost drivers influencing cost of electric powertrain as a whole. Within these components, if we consider e.g. the battery pack, there are elements such as chemistry of the battery that is not manageable for cost reduction purposes, and other components that, instead, have less constraints regarding cost reduction. Taking in mind this scenario and the solutions adopted in the RESOLVE, it may be useful classify cost drivers along two criteria (Figure 4 and 5):

- Impact on cost (it represents “How much the specific cost driver impact on cost object)
- Manageability (it represents “How much the specific organization can influence the cost driver impact”)

The Cost Driver Matrix can be developed and filled referring to cost object at different levels (more general or more analytic). Maybe the electric powertrain considered as a whole could be positioned in the quadrant High impact on costs

Figure 4. A matrix for component cost driver selection (electric powertrain)

Figure 5. A matrix for component cost drivers selection (components of electric powertrain)

The level may be high or low. The cost drivers set in “high-high” quadrant are those that mostly affect cost of cost object and those mostly manageable by the organization (the organization has margins to reduce their impact on the cost object). About “impact on costs”, at early stage of NPD (the case of RESOLVE project) often there is not detailed cost information since many technological issues (e.g. vehicle architecture) have still to be defined. However, it could be useful to have just a rough estimation of costs amount (e.g. a percentage of component cost on total cost of product) in order to classify each components in several quadrants. This is the reason because also a partial cost information as marginal cost may be useful rather than more complete and accurate full cost configuration.

About manageability, it is necessary to understand if and how much the organization can intervene in these components in modifying them to gain cost savings. In RESOLVE project the analysis of electric powertrain, considered as a first level cost driver, highlights chances for facing the cost constraints. In fact, some of its components can be more or less manageable depending on their features. For example, referring to battery pack, some of its characteristics cannot be managed (e.g. chemistry) while other can, e.g. the size could be reduced, other components of the battery pack that can be redesigned. Hence, the decomposition of the cost driver considered as whole (the electric powertrain) in its components, and in turn an additional decomposition of these components in sub-cost drivers categories, allows locating some sub-cost drivers in their own quadrant. Doing so, it is possible identify alternative cost reduction solutions.

Analysis of empirical evidences shows that impact of relevant cost drivers may be more effectively examined decomposing them in sub-categories that better explain cost trend, cost behavior and possible levers to move for cost reduction/management purposes.

Within RESOLVE case study, the technology has been selected (electrical vehicles) and it is not modifiable. The most relevant cost driver within the adopted technology seems to be the product design configuration, included both in Porter and in Riley’s taxonomy. Referring to electric powertrain this generic cost driver may be decomposed in sub-categories according to particular aspects of component’s design configuration. Doing so, the whole “product design configuration” for

specific components becomes a modular, scalable, functional integrated and low cost design configuration, as described within Grant Agreement and reported in the previous section. Once we get to the identification of relevant cost drivers in the context examined, tracing back the "path", we define the selection process as follows:

Empirical evidence	General step for cost driver analysis
<p><i>“European cities are increasingly congested due to the increased demand and usage of motor vehicles of a growing urban population. (...) As these vehicles become more numerous, emissions increase, parking gets scarcer, and noise levels pollute the urban air. These factors affect the quality of life and health of city-dwellers”.</i></p> <p><i>“Efforts have been taken to encourage the uptake of hybrid and fully electric vehicles. Narrow-track Electric L-category Vehicles (ELVs) that emit less, taking up less space and being quieter than cars. Although the rate of adoption of these vehicles is not high enough to have a significant impact on the attainment of emission targets, or an improvement in urban living conditions”.</i></p> <p><i>RESOLVE aims at enabling the development of a range of cost-effective, energy efficient and comfortable ELVs that will entice ICE car drivers to switch from cars to ELVs for their daily urban commutes.</i></p> <p><i>“To facilitate a larger uptake of ELVs, they have to become more attractive to current urban drivers. Besides the urban policies regarding ELVs that could be changed to encourage large scale ELV adoption, four limiting factors have to be overcome. The cost, energy efficiency, attractiveness of ELVs and drivers who will consider ELVs as alternatives will be addressed by RESOLVE.”</i></p> <p>RESOLVE is defined a RIA project (see definition in “empirical domain and case findings” section)</p>	<p>1. Defining main characteristics of empirical domain and cost problem/constraints to be faced according to the purposes of cost driver analysis (e.g. cost reduction, efficiency measurement, value chain reconfiguration and so on)</p>
<p><i>“RESOLVE aims to make powertrains for future ELVs less costly by reducing the marginal unit manufacturing cost of the powertrain modules (...)”</i></p> <p><i>“We aim to reduce the marginal unit manufacturing cost of our (omissis) reference design (omissis) to (omissis), down from (omissis), for design volumes of (omissis) units/year”.</i></p>	<p>2. Identifying cost object (product/services or production inputs) and cost information to be adopted (e.g. marginal cost, manufacturing or full cost), depending on purposes of cost driver analysis and contextual variables.</p>

<p><i>“Marginal unit manufacturing costs of electric powertrains are comprised of three main components: the battery pack, drivetrain electronics and electric motor.”</i></p>	<p>3. If it is necessary, decomposing cost object in sub-components, simpler than the whole, that impact on cost of the cost object, but where cost issues may be easier to face (and to overcome). These components may be considered as cost drivers. Here, it’s possible to support the selection of cost drivers considering their manageability and impact on cost.</p>
<p><i>“Within RESOLVE we focus on reducing the cost of the drivetrain electronics (...)” by achieving functional integration (...)”</i></p> <p><i>“Further cost savings will be obtained through the economies of scale from using the modular and scalable design of the components.”</i></p> <p><i>“We will indirectly reduce the cost of energy storage by designing modular battery architecture and by reducing the required battery capacity for a target range through energy-saving measures (...)”</i></p> <p><i>“RESOLVE will look to integrate components into clusters. The components that RESOLVE would integrate are the inverter, battery charger, DC/DC converter, and VMU, as well as the BMS into the battery pack. Also, other solutions such as the integration of inverter and e-motor will be explored as viable alternatives. The innovative combination will radically reduce costs”.</i></p>	<p>4. Identifying solutions for cost reduction.</p>
<p><i>“Within RESOLVE we focus on reducing the cost of the drivetrain electronics (comprised of inverter, DC/DC-converter, battery charger and vehicle management unit), by achieving functional integration of all these electronic functions into one configurable Drivetrain Management Module (DMM). Further cost savings will be obtained through the economies of scale from using the modular and scalable design of the components”</i></p> <p><i>“We will indirectly reduce the cost of energy storage by designing modular battery architecture and by reducing the required battery capacity for a target range through energy-saving measures (...)”</i></p>	<p>5. Identifying cause and effect relationships between cost of the whole cost object and cost of its sub-components</p>

Table 1. Empirical Evidences and general steps for cost driver analysis

Furthermore, properly cost driver selection (and management) depend on how cost information has been determined and which cost configuration is taken into account (Risso et al., 2016). For example, if we consider marginal, manufacturing or full cost, relevant cost drivers may be different.

Empirical evidences show that within RESOLVE project a marginal and a partial full cost approach was adopted, since due to specific features of the project (RIA) and the high degree of uncertainty at these early stages, it seemed suitable to use simple cost concept to communicate in a clear manner the goals of the project.

Conclusions, limitations and further researches

Through analysis of case findings, it seems that cost drivers defined at strategic level at more general level according to the Porter and Riley s' framework can be useful during the first stage of NPD. In fact, in those stages there is still a high degree of market, technological and project scope uncertainty, where often only a rough estimation of cost data is available. In addition, it is relevant to take into account that the RESOLVE project is a RIA; hence, its focus is not on the marketability of its output. These contextual factors could make cost information on cost drivers more useful in an aggregate form just to have a signal of their amount. Furthermore, case findings show the relevance of product design configuration, a well-known cost driver that may be fruitful investigating more deeply to understand how to manage it. The empirical evidences highlight at least two elements: i) a possible process to analyze the product design configuration considered as a first level cost driver; ii) the role of cost information in this process.

i) A possible process to analyze the product design configuration.

In the RESOLVE case study, the cost constraint has been faced focusing the effort on the electric powertrain, just a (core) sub-system of the vehicle. This component has been divided in sub components, hence, the first lesson that can be learned from RESOLVE is “*decomposing the product components could be useful to find way to reduce their cost.*”

After decomposition of electronic powertrain, RESOLVE project proposes to adopt modularity, scalability and functional integration as approaches to reduce costs of its sub-components. So, which other lessons can be learned from these choices of product design configuration. Product design configuration's features influence the value chain activities, determining which activity it is necessary to control and which cost drivers (“first level” cost drivers such as scale economies) it is possible to manage for reducing costs. Modularity, for instance, allows having a battery composed by modules, avoiding repeating development activities (and relative costs) for batteries with different power and reducing incidence of manufacturing cost on the single unit (battery module) with potential scale economies, and full capacity utilization of the battery supplier. Finally, this solution contributes to reduce product end-user price. Doing so, this feature of product design configuration, specifically battery design configuration, becomes both a cost driver that puts in evidence how product design configuration affects value chain costs and a solution to reduce costs. The next Figure highlights cost drivers, stages of the process of cost driver analysis and the relationship among relevant cost driver in our empirical domain.

Figure 6. The linkages among Product design configuration and other cost drivers

Figure 6 shows that product design configuration is determined by the Business Unit strategy (Banker and Johnston, 2007). In the case study herein developed, this strategy regards the purposes of OEMs involved in the project that is to be competitive within the market of ELVs. OEMs objectives in terms of strategies are considered as given and they are not discussed in this paper.

Linkages among product design configuration and other elements included in the figure (steps 3; 4; 5) show a possible process to find relevant cost driver for product cost reduction. Decomposing product design configuration may be a way to identify solutions such as modularity, scalability, functional integration and so on that permit to link product design configuration as a generic cost drivers to the other ones (scale economies, capacity utilization and so on). Modularity, scalability and functional integration are well known in cost management (Davila and Wouters, 2004) and in literature about cost design reduction (Ehrlenspiel et al., 2010). However, herein these approaches are analyzed and discussed jointly with cost drivers coming from strategic and management accounting literature, specifying their causal linkage. Furthermore, the RESOLVE case study highlights that cost management initiatives could be applied also in the early stages of NPD and to the core of the value proposition (core components of the product) and not only “around” it (Davila and Wouters, 2004; 2007).

ii) The role of cost information in the analysis of cost drivers.

Although the high-sounding title, this last section aims above all to propose a research note. Our remarks focus mainly on what it has been stated in the RESOLVE Grant Agreement about the marginal cost of drivetrain electronics. Strategic management accounting literature highlights shortcomings and limits the adoption of marginal cost for strategic decisions (e.g. Shank and Govindarajan, 1996). It is also possible that within RESOLVE case study there was an inappropriate usage of marginal cost and thus it would be the “exception confirming the rule”. However, it seems that marginal cost in Grant Agreement of the project was voluntarily used just to have a primary idea of the amount of manageable cost of the ELV under development. In this context, due to the huge amount of unmanageable fixed costs (cost reduction per unit depends on the possibilities to exploit commonalities), marginal cost could have an usefulness, above all in the early stages of NPD, when having more “full” cost information often it is not possible, and maybe not necessary.

Also, preliminary cost analysis carried out in these early stages of the project, showed that due to the high degree of technological, market and project scope uncertainty it is not possible and useful having detailed cost information. Furthermore, at this stage it is sufficient a rough estimation of costs, in order to allow partners to identify possible levers for cost reduction. Hence, at early stages of a NPD process, such as that developed within a RIA, a simple cost calculation, ranging from marginal cost to a “partial full cost” could provide useful insights for the next development activities. This could be a matter needing more investigation through further researches.

Of course this study has some limitations. First, we did not investigate yet cost drivers accounting, or in other words, the “quantitative side” of cost driver issues in terms of the measurement of the impact of costs reduction initiatives on total cost of the vehicle. Secondly, to date we did not measure the impact of shared resources on total cost of the vehicle. In the next steps of the project it will be necessary taking into account the opportunity to apply RESOLVE’s solutions to a wide range of next generation full ELVs and defining if and how these common costs will be allocated to products. Then, another limitation of this research is the lack of the market test to verify if the construction works (Kasanen et. al, 1993).

Other further researches could: i) test the method for managing and selecting cost drivers in other case study to verify if it works; ii) test the construct in other stages of NPD and in different context, e.g. other manufacturing industry or also in service sector; iii) investigate if the construct works or how it has to be modified, considering activities rather than cost object (e.g., in order to redesign firm’s value chain).

In addition, topics dealing with managing indirect cost in the early stages of NPD and the effect of commonality policies on the design of costing system, herein partially explored, represent a rich field for further researches (Wouters and Davila, 2007: 835).

Acknowledgments

The authors express gratitude to the personnel of companies involved in the RESOLVE project who cooperate to this paper. Thanks we also due to the Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation, which by RESOLVE project founded the research on which this paper is based.

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